

About FAIRmat

FAIR data

To fully realize the potential of research data, we need to make them FAIR: **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**e-purposable.

This allows data to be understood and (re)used by the entire community.

A FAIR approach will not only make current research more testable and reproducible, but opens the doors to new ways of doing science through the application of machine learning and artificial intelligence.

Our mission

We provide scientists with a FAIR data infrastructure and the skills and tools they need to make the most of it. Our mission has two parts:

1. Develop and maintain a federated FAIR data infrastructure for materials data with built-in tools and standards to support scientific collaboration and proper research data management (RDM) practices.
2. Support the scientific community to introduce and maintain high standards of reproducibility, research integrity, and compliance with ethical and legal requirements by adopting proper RDM practices based on the FAIR data principles.

Our services

NOMAD

Our free web service lets you share your data or use comprehensive data that others provide. You can use NOMAD to organize, analyze, share, and publish your materials science data, as well as explore, download, and analyze your colleagues' data.

NOMAD Oasis

Create your own NOMAD! Get an instant overview of all your group's data, increase productivity, and implement research data management plans with ease.

NOMAD Encyclopedia

See, compare, explore, and understand materials data.

AI Toolkit

Run notebooks to analyze the data contained in the NOMAD Archive with AI tools.

Training and Education

We offer training and educational materials on research data management and all of the NOMAD features and services.

FAIRmat

FAIR DATA

INFRASTRUCTURE FOR
CONDENSED-MATTER
PHYSICS AND
THE CHEMICAL PHYSICS OF
SOLIDS

www.fairmat-nfdi.eu

Gefördert durch

Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

How we work

Area G deals with the internal organization and the team spirit of the consortium. This includes scientific and administrative coordination as well as interaction with the NFDI.

Area F engages with the community to raise awareness and acceptance of FAIR research data management, and ensures that concepts, tools, and infrastructure developed by FAIRmat meet the needs of the scientific community and are easy to adopt. It provides information and training, and reaches out to the community for ideas and feedback.

Area E is demonstrating how the FAIRmat data infrastructure supports the research of the materials science community by creating use cases that show how the tools developed by FAIRmat support the research of various sub-communities.

FAIRmat is governed by internationally renowned researchers, who are actively embedded into their (sub)communities. Its infrastructure is developed by a dedicated team of coworkers with complimentary expertise. The organization is divided into seven Areas, each addressing specific key aspects of the project.

Area D lays the foundation of a federated research data infrastructure for the condensed-matter and chemical-physics community. It aims at enabling individual scientists and research institutes to manage large amounts of heterogeneous data from a variety of sources following common principles.

Area A is making sample synthesis reproducible by finding hidden synthesis parameters, accelerating the development of novel materials by devising synthesis recipes, and making characterization data of synthesized materials assessable.

Area B is building a complete research data management cycle for experimental solid state physics and the physical chemistry of solids by developing concepts for a FAIR research data management. Our mission is to comprehensively and systematically describe experimental methods to contain all data and metadata necessary for detailed comparability of different experiments.

Area C has integrated the NOMAD Laboratory into FAIRmat and is significantly enhancing its infrastructure and services by adding recent *ab initio* advancements, classical simulations, multiscale modeling, and excited states methodology. It also prepares the incorporation of other theoretical methods.